

ARC-DPA model calibration for simil AIM1 austenitic steel

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to achieve a more accurate assessment of radiation damage in a structural steel for Fast Reactors through model calibration. Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations were performed to characterise primary radiation damage in a FeCrNi solid-solution modelling the AIM1 austenitic steel. The threshold displacement energy (TDE) was first evaluated for Fe, Cr, and Ni primary knock-on atoms (PKAs) along uniformly distributed directions, providing the basis for quantifying defect production under irradiation. Despite the compositional complexity, the three atomic species exhibit similar behavior, suggesting a limited influence of alloying. The evolution of defect production with increasing PKA energy reveals two distinct regimes: up to about 10 keV, damage is dominated by isolated Frenkel pairs, while at higher energies, extended clustering prevails. Within the first energy regime, the ARC (Athermal Recombination Corrected) model reproduces the MD results more accurately than the traditional NRT approach, highlighting the need to update damage models for a more realistic description of defect production in FeCrNi alloys.

Keywords: FeCrNi Alloy, Threshold Displacement Energy, ARC model, Molecular Dynamics

1. INTRODUCTION

The combined challenge of global warming mitigation, increasing energy demand, and the pursuit of energy security has reignited the discourse around nuclear energy, valued for its ability to provide large-scale, reliable and low-carbon power [1]. Generation IV fast-spectrum reactors are of particular interest for their potential to improve fuel utilization and enable fuel cycle closure [2], though they also expose structural steels to higher neutron fluxes and temperatures, accelerating radiation-induced degradation [3].

Alongside the development of more resistant steels, significant effort is devoted to improving radiation damage models. In metals, damage originates from displacement cascades, triggered when a neutron transfers energy above the Threshold Displacement Energy (TDE) to a lattice atom, creating a primary knock-on atom (PKA) that can initiate further displacements. The outcome of this processes is the formation of defects, including vacancy–interstitial (Frenkel) pairs. Given the short time and length scales involved, direct experimental observation of the displacement cascade is not feasible, and computational models have become essential to predict the number of point defects created by a PKA. This quantity is directly related to the evaluation of displacements per atom (dpa), the most widely adopted metric to quantify radiation damage, as the damage energy lost by neutrons in materials, computed in neutron transport simulations, must be related to corresponding material degradation. The standard estimation of the number of point defects N_d^{NRT} as a function of the PKA damage energy T is provided by the NRT model [4], derived from binary collision approximation calculations:

$$N_d^{\text{NRT}}(T) = \frac{0.8 T}{2E_d}, \quad (1)$$

where E_d is the material TDE. Despite its simplicity, this formulation is well known to overestimate the number of surviving defects [5, 6], as it neglects their recombination occurring during the displacement cascade. Building on the direct counting of point defects obtained from molecular dynamics simulations of cascades, Nordlund et al. [7] developed a corrective formulation to the NRT law. The Athermal Recombination-Corrected (ARC) model accounts for athermal recombination processes, providing a more realistic description of primary damage. The model is described as follows:

$$N_d^{\text{arc}}(T) = N_d^{\text{NRT}}(T) \left[\frac{1 - c_{\text{arc}}}{(2E_d/0.8)^{b_{\text{arc}}}} T^{b_{\text{arc}}} + c_{\text{arc}} \right], \quad (2)$$

where c_{arc} and b_{arc} are material-specific parameters obtained from MD simulations. Despite the improvements of the ARC model, its development has so far been limited to few metals or oxides but seldom to alloys. To extend its applicability to more complex systems, the present work aims to calibrate the ARC model for a solid modelling AIM1 austenitic steel. A series of molecular dynamics simulations were carried out on an Fe₇₀Cr₁₅Ni₁₅ solid solution to assess the TDE. Several displacement cascades with PKA energies ranging from a few hundreds of eV up to 30 keV were also conducted to derive the additional parameters used in the ARC model. This study thus provides the necessary parameters for applying the ARC model to a technologically relevant alloy and illustrates the quantitative differences in predictions between the NRT and ARC. Accurate evaluation of radiation damage in structural materials is particularly useful for small pool-type LFRs where internal components are exposed to high radiation, enabling cost-effective design without compromising safety.

The remainder of the paper outlines the methodology adopted for the TDE analysis and ARC model calibration (Section 2), presents and discusses the main results (Section 3), and concludes with final remarks (Section 4).

2. METHODS

Classical MD simulations of displacement cascades were performed with LAMMPS [8] (v. 2Aug2023) in a Fe–Cr–Ni (70–15–15 at.%) face-centred cubic (fcc) random solid solution, modelling AIM1 austenitic steel. Interactions were described using a combination of the Béland EAM potential [9] and the ZBL universal potential [10] at short interatomic distances. The cell was thermalised at 300 K under constant pressure and temperature for 50 ps before triggering the cascade. Variable timesteps were employed to ensure accurate trajectory reconstruction. During the displacement cascade, atoms were relaxed under microcanonical ensemble, namely conserving the number of atoms, the volume and the total energy. The absorption of the excess kinetic energy produced during the cascade was ensured by rescaling the velocities of the atoms located within the 3 Å-thick outer layer of the simulation box to maintain the system temperature at 300 K. The cascade itself was considered concluded when the total energy was stable for more than 30 ps for higher energy cascades ($E_{\text{PKA}} > 5$ keV), or for 5 ps otherwise.

The TDE value, defined as the minimum energy required to create a stable defect (either a Frenkel pair or an atomic replacement) was determined for each atomic species using a binary search algorithm [11]: the energy range (0–200 eV) was iteratively refined by halving or increasing the PKA energy depending on defect formation, until the threshold displacement energy was determined with an accuracy of 2 eV. For each species (Fe, Cr, Ni), 25 PKAs were randomly selected from the innermost cell volume (55 Å, 16,384 atoms) and displaced along 200 recoil directions, quasi-uniformly distributed in a half-sphere using the spherical Fibonacci lattice [12]. This approach accounted for the dependence of TDE on the local atomic environment, recoil direction and type, ensuring statistical accuracy. Defect identification was performed after ~2 ps of cascade evolution by an algorithm implementing a constant cutoff Wigner–Seitz analysis. The TDE value for each species i was obtained as an angular average of the directional values $E_{d,i}(\theta, \phi)$ using the following expression [13]:

$$\overline{E_{d,i}} = \frac{\int_0^\pi \int_0^\pi E_{d,i}(\theta, \phi) \sin \theta d\theta d\phi}{\int_0^\pi \int_0^\pi \sin \theta d\theta d\phi}, \quad (3)$$

Table I. Summary of cascade simulation setup.

PKA energy [keV]	Cell size[Å]	Atoms[#]	Runs	Time[ps]
0.5	100	87.808	10	~16
1	100	87.808	10	~22
2	100	87.808	10	~22
5	200	740.772	10	~155
10	290	2.205.474	10	~185
20	330	3.322.336	10	~210
30	350	3.881.196	5	~280

where the subscript i refers to the PKA species. The TDE for the alloy was calculated as a weighted average over the atomic fractions. Two complementary methods (crystallographic directions and displacement probability curves) were also considered for validation.

For the calibration of the ARC model, displacement cascades were simulated for PKA energies ranging from 0.5 to 30 keV, with PKAs initialized along the [135] crystallographic direction to minimize channeling effects. For each energy and PKA species, several independent runs were performed (Tab. I). Simulation cell sizes were scaled with the PKA energy to avoid cascade self-interaction that could happen due to periodic boundary conditions. For the cascade analysis, point defects were identified using the Wigner-Seitz method implemented in OVITO [14] (v. 3.1.3), based on Voronoi cell occupancy. Cascade morphology was examined through cluster analysis and the Dislocation Extraction Algorithm (DXA), enabling the visualization and classification of extended defects. Complementary identification with the topological approach in the ACME code [15] (v. 4.1.4.2) provided a more complete description of the defect population. The resulting data were further processed in OVITO to exclude clustered defects, already observed at 10 keV, and retain only the surviving point defects relevant for ARC calibration.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. TDE Analysis

The determination of the ternary FeCrNi TDE relies on the cascades generated by Fe, Cr, and Ni PKAs. The directional analysis reveal a bimodal distribution for all three species, with a low energy peak at ≈ 40 eV and a higher one at ≈ 90 eV for Fe and ≈ 65 eV for Cr and Ni (see Fig. 1(a)). Ni shows the dominant peak at lower energies, while Fe exhibits the broadest distribution, ranging from 20 eV to 110 eV. Despite such differences, the TDE contour plots and elevation angle distribution (Fig. 1(b)) show a similar overall trend for all three PKAs, as expected given their comparable mass. The TDE map for the FeCrNi solid solution in Fig. 1(c) shows a gradual increase from the less packed directions to the more densely packed surrounding of [112] direction. This trend is consistent with previous evaluations (e.g., [16]), although the presence of high-energy peaks, particularly for Fe, results in a higher average TDE values for the solid solution, which is 60.77 eV (Tab. II, first line). To consolidate these results, the TDE was also evaluated through crystallographic and probabilistic approaches. In the former, the PKA was displaced along the j fundamental crystallographic directions [100], [111], [110] and [112], with the average TDE value for each PKA species i computed as a weighted mean of the directional TDE values $E_{d,i}^j$ [17]:

$$\overline{E_{d,i}^c} = \sum_j c_j E_{d,i}^j, \quad (4)$$

where the weights c_j are the number of equivalent directions (6, 8, 12, and 12, respectively). In the probabilistic approach, the TDE is interpreted as an energy range where the defect creation probability smoothly increases from 0 to 1, reflecting the stochastic nature of displacement processes [13]. For the same crystallographic directions, the PKAs' energy was gradually increased to construct the probability

Figure 1. Histograms of TDE values for Cr, Fe, and Ni PKAs in the FeCrNi solid solution (a), together with their distribution along the elevation angle (b). Red circles, blue squares and green triangles represent TDE values of Fe, Cr and Ni, respectively. Image (c) is the contour plot of the TDE surface included in the crystallographic directions [100], [110], [111] for the solid solution FeCrNi.

Table II. Average TDE values for Fe, Cr, Ni and the FeCrNi solid solution derived from the directional scan (\overline{E}_d), the crystallographic approach (\overline{E}_d^C), and the logistic (\overline{E}_d^S) and lowest value \overline{E}_d^m fits on the propability curves.

TDE[eV]	Fe	Cr	Ni	FeCrNi
\overline{E}_d	64.20±0.41	54.66±0.31	50.88±0.33	60.77±0.30
\overline{E}_d^C	59.90±1.92	51.91±1.57	53.11±1.90	57.69±1.39
\overline{E}_d^S	58.94±0.59	50.41±0.23	51.98±0.39	56.64±0.52
\overline{E}_d^m	32.52±0.34	36.70±0.26	35.13±0.32	33.54±0.24

curves shown in Fig. 2. The probability curve for [100] is steep and shifted toward lower energies, while [111] is smoother and at higher energies, consistent with the TDE map in Fig. 1. For each PKA type, $\overline{E}_{d,i}^S$ was extracted by fitting the results with a logistic function and identifying the TDE as the energy corresponding to a 50% chance of defect creation. For a more conservative TDE estimate, the probability curves were also fit with a lowest value model where the threshold energy $E_{d,i}^m$ corresponds to the energy at which the probability becomes non-zero [18].

The crystallographic and logistic approaches give consistent results, with differences below 2% (Tab. II), but both yield values 5–7% lower than the full directional scan. This discrepancy reflects the restriction to principal crystallographic directions, where the TDE is lower, leading to a slight underestimation of the average. As expected, the lowest value fit produces the smallest value, consistent with previous works (e.g., [16]). This highlights that the differences between results stem from the adopted definition of TDE rather than from flaws in the potential used or the analysis itself. The directional scan provides the most representative picture of the TDE landscape for the FeCrNi solid solution, but, in engineering applications, often the most conservative approach is preferred and the \overline{E}_d^m value should be used.

3.2. Contribution of electronic energy loss

An atom moving in a metal loses energy both through collisions with surrounding atoms and via electronic excitation or ionisation, with electronic energy loss becoming more relevant as the PKA energy

Figure 2. Displacement probability curves and fitted logistic functions for Fe (red dots), Cr (blue squares), and Ni (green triangles) PKAs along [100] (left) and [111] (right).

increases. While this effect can be neglected in TDE evaluations, where the energies involved are only a few tens of eV and ballistic processes dominate, it was necessary to estimate its influence when considering higher PKA energies for the calibration of the ARC model.

For this purpose, the open-source Monte Carlo ion transport code Iradina [19, 20] (v. 1.2.3) was employed. Based on the binary collision approximation, Iradina follows the PKA trajectory collision by collision, solving the scattering integral to update its energy and direction. The energy loss to electrons is accounted for through pre-tabulated data from the SRIM module SRModule.exe [10], which provides semi-empirical stopping powers derived from experimental measurements and physical models. Using the same Fe₇₀Cr₁₅Ni₁₅ composition adopted in the MD simulations and PKA energies, the transport of 10,000 Fe, Cr, and Ni ions was simulated, each repeated with ten different random seeds to ensure statistical accuracy. Since Iradina does not construct an explicit crystalline lattice and treats the material as a statistically homogeneous medium, the initial direction of the PKAs is not relevant. Damage calculation was omitted to only evaluate the energy partition between electronic and ballistic losses.

The results in Tab. III show that the fraction of the initial PKA energy dissipated into electronic stopping is $\approx 5\%$, exceeding this value only after 10 keV. This confirmed that the contribution of electronic energy loss is negligible compared to ballistic losses. Consequently, the electronic stopping effect was not explicitly included in the molecular dynamics simulations performed with LAMMPS in the following, expecting that the changes in the number of defects produced would not be significant.

Table III. Percent fraction of PKA energy lost in electronic (R_{e1}) and ballistic (R_b) effects in FeCrNi. Values in parentheses indicate one standard error in the last digit(s).

PKA energy[keV]	0.5	1	2	5	10	20	30
$R_{e1}[\%]$	4.789(3)	4.574(4)	4.573(5)	4.904(6)	5.413(6)	6.298(6)	7.024(10)
$R_b[\%]$	95.211(3)	95.426(4)	95.427(5)	95.096(6)	94.587(6)	93.704(6)	92.976(10)

3.3. ARC model Calibration

For the FeCrNi solid solution, the calibration of the ARC model was complicated by the defect morphology produced after the displacement cascades. At PKA energies up to 10 keV, the damage was dominated by isolated point defects, i.e., the type of defects that can be described by the NRT or ARC formulations in Eq. (1) and Eq. (2), respectively. Above this threshold, the behaviour changed considerably. Cascades at 20 keV and 30 keV exhibited extensive clustering and nanophase formation, as exemplified in Fig. 3 where, along simple point defects, planar and even 3D agglomerates of defects

can be identified. A cluster analysis performed with OVITO considering a cutoff value of 2.5 Å showed that at 20 keV about 92.7% of the defects were aggregated into clusters larger than 12 atoms, with an average cluster size of 23.5 atoms. At 30 keV, this fraction increased to 97.7%, with the average cluster containing 32.6 atoms. These highly complex defect structures are not point-like in nature and therefore lie outside the descriptive domain of the ARC formulation. Moreover, their analysis through the Wigner–Seitz approach appeared problematic, as entire nanophase regions were counted as defects, resulting in the overestimation of their number. For comparison, in 10 keV cascades 47.1% of the defects were in clusters larger than 12 atoms, with an average cluster size of 17.5 atoms.

Figure 3. Example of ACME analysis for a 30 keV cascade. Red markers denote dislocation nodes, yellow interstitials, and blue vacancies. Defects are represented together with dislocation lines (green are Shockley, yellow Hirth and pink Stair-rod), as obtained with the OVITO DXA analysis. Planar and 3D clusters were excluded, while split interstitials were adjusted to ensure proper counting.

Figure 4. Comparison of defect production in FeCrNi cascades. The NRT model (black) systematically overestimates the number of defects, while both ACME (red) and Wigner–Seitz (green) analyses follow the sub-linear behavior and are well reproduced by the ARC fit.

For these reasons, the quantitative calibration of the ARC model was restricted to cascades up to 10 keV, where the sub-linear defect production expected from the theory is still observed. A direct comparison between ACME and Wigner–Seitz analyses in this energy range (Fig. 4) showed differences consistent within propagated uncertainties ($<2\sigma$ across all energies). In both cases, the number of surviving defects in the FeCrNi solid solution was significantly lower than what predicted by the NRT model, confirming its systematic overestimation especially at higher PKA energies. The calibration of the ARC model, performed considering the minimum TDE value $\bar{E}_d^m = 33.54$ eV, provided a more accurate description of the observed number of Frenkel pairs. The best-fit parameters obtained from the analysis done using ACME for the FeCrNi solid solution are

$$c_{arc} = -0.106 \pm 0.0496 \quad b_{arc} = -0.338 \pm 0.034,$$

which have the order of magnitude of the values reported in the literature [7] for the individual constituents of the alloy. This indicates that the alloying effect had only a limited influence on defect production under the simulation conditions used in this study. This conclusion is supported by the spatial distribution analysis of atomic species within the cascade region, which showed that the local concentrations of Fe, Cr, and Ni remain consistent with the nominal alloy composition, without evidence of segregation. At higher temperatures, however, enhanced defect mobility and solute diffusion could amplify alloy-specific effects, potentially modifying the recombination dynamics and the resulting ARC behavior.

While the ARC formulation is formally valid within the regime of isolated point defects — found here

to extend up to about 10 keV — this restriction is not expected to strongly affect its applicability, as the majority of PKAs in iron should have comparable energies. In fact, even in fast-reactor conditions, the neutron–atom interactions are dominated by elastic scattering, which limits the fraction of energy transferred to the recoil atom and results in PKA spectra that are strongly weighted toward low energies. A detailed characterization of the PKA energy spectrum would be useful to clarify this point and quantify the fraction of higher-energy recoils. Overall, although not a definitive model, the ARC formulation provides a far more physically consistent estimate of defect production than the conventional NRT approach.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study employed molecular dynamics simulations to determine the threshold displacement energy of the FeCrNi solid solution modelling of AIM1 austenitic steel, and to calibrate the parameters of the ARC model for this alloy. A directional scan of recoil trajectories yielded a higher average TDE than simplified crystallographic or probabilistic estimates, while a lowest value fit produced the most conservative values. For PKA energies below 10 keV, defect production followed the expected sublinear trend with energy and remained substantially lower than NRT predictions, confirming the systematic overestimation of the model. The ARC model reproduced the observed number of surviving Frenkel pairs and the results are consistent with the values reported in the literature for the elemental constituents. No significant alloying effects on either TDE or ARC response were observed in the investigated composition and temperature. At higher PKA energies, cascades exhibit extensive clustering and nanophase formation beyond ARC's point-defect regime, motivating the present calibration limit of 10 keV. Despite this restriction, the calibrated parameters are expected to remain representative of the behaviour of most PKAs, although this aspect requires further investigation.

Given the clustering observed at higher energies, ARC could be complemented with metrics that go beyond the traditional dpa-based formulations and explicitly account for defect morphology. Moreover, model validation under operating conditions relevant to Generation IV reactors—including realistic PKA spectra, elevated temperatures, and long-timescale defect evolution—could help quantify when clustering and alloy-specific effects become non-negligible, and whether extensions of ARC or multi-scale coupling to microstructural models are warranted.

While not a fully comprehensive model of irradiation damage, the ARC formulation calibrated against MD simulations provides a physically consistent and practical framework for estimating primary damage and supporting the design of structural components in fast-spectrum systems. Although the present simulations are based on a simple FeCrNi solid solution and do not capture the full microstructural complexity of AIM1—such as minor alloying elements, precipitates, or interfaces—the resulting trends are expected to be representative of the material response. Future studies extending this approach to higher temperatures and to conditions involving local stress or strain fields would help bridge the gap toward more realistic reactor environments.

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